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OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study primarily aimed to examine the effect of operational efficiency on the financial performance of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria. The research design adopted in this study was ex post facto research, secondary data were employed, and a population of 13 companies was used. The sample size was 11 purposively selected companies. Pooled OLS regression analysis was used to analyze the data, and STATA 17 was employed as the statistical package. The analysis results revealed that inventory turnover has a significant positive effect on the return on capital employed; receivable turnover has a significant positive effect on the return on capital employed; and noncurrent assets turnover has a significant positive effect on the return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Thus, it was concluded that operational efficiency has a significant effect on the financial performance of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria. Therefore, companies should implement robust strategies to optimize inventory levels, such as improved forecasting techniques, efficient supply chain management, and just-in-time inventory systems, feasible, to minimize holding costs and enhance cash flow.

Keywords: Operational efficiency, financial performance, inventory turnover, receivable turnover and noncurrent assets turnover.

1.0 Introduction

The operational activities are the life wire of business entities, and thus, any company's management endeavors to ensure that these activities are adequately optimized. Efficient operations enable companies to minimize waste, reduce costs, and maximize productivity, thereby enhancing financial outcomes. One of the critical factors that determine an organization's ability to sustain growth and remain competitive is its operating efficiency. Operating efficiency, which is an entity's capacity to effectively utilize inputs to produce output at a minimal cost, encompasses inventory turnover, receivable turnover, non-current asset utilization, cost control, labor productivity, and process optimization (Abdillah, 2020). According to Olarewaju and Sanusi et al. (2020),

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efficiency measures how well a company can turn financial resources into goods and services at a reduced cost relative to the income it generates. Companies that maintain their operating efficiency well have a chance of surviving in a harsh economic environment.

Operational efficiency can be accessed through inventory turnover, receivable turnover, and noncurrent asset turnover. Inventory turnover indicates how efficiently a company manages its inventory by measuring the number of times inventory is sold and replaced over a period of time. Receivable turnover reflects how quickly a company collects its accounts receivable. A higher turnover implies efficient credit and collection policies, leading to a quicker conversion of sales into cash. Noncurrent asset turnover measures how effectively a company utilizes its noncurrent assets to generate revenue (Koross & Nyaoga, 2024). A higher ratio indicates that the company is generating more sales per naira of assets, indicating efficient asset use.

Financial performance is a measure of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms. It indicates a company's ability to generate profits and manage its financial resources. These results are reflected in the firm's ROI, ROA, shareholder value, accounting profitability, and its components. Efficiency in an organization's operations relates to the optimum utilization of its resources to achieve greater output (Owolabi & Obida, 2022). A higher inventory turnover generally indicates that a company is quickly selling its inventory, which also reduces inventory holding costs. These cost savings directly contribute to higher profits. Rapid sales convert inventory into cash more quickly, improving the company's liquidity and reducing the need for short-term borrowing, thereby lowering interest expenses. A higher receivable turnover indicates that a company efficiently collects its dues from customers on credit sales. This results in a quicker conversion of sales into cash. When companies' operational efficiency increases, it tends to reduce working capital spending and thus increase the company's financial sustainability. Consequently, operational efficiency impacts both a company's current profitability and its potential for future performance, serving as a proxy for competitive advantage (Nyakieni, 2022). A higher noncurrent assets turnover ratio signifies that a company effectively utilizes its noncurrent assets to generate sales revenue. Thus, this study examined the effect of operational efficiency on the financial performance of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria.

A company's operating efficiency, often reflected in its inventory, receivables, and noncurrent asset utilization management, is a critical determinant of its financial health and sustainability. Suboptimal performance in these areas can lead to significant financial distress, impacting liquidity, profitability, and long-term growth. Despite the benefits of operational efficiency on financial performance, many businesses find managing their core operational processes difficult. A decline in key efficiency metrics such as inventory turnover, receivable turnover, and noncurrent asset turnover signals deteriorating financial outcomes. A thorough examination of Nigerian business trends over time reveals a consistent rise in costs and a decline in profits. This raises the question of why so many industrial businesses in the country struggle with operational efficiency.

The empirical studies reviewed showed some gaps. There is a dearth of research in this area as scanty empirical studies were seen. The few empirical studies available focused on other sectors of the economy, such as banks and agricultural firms (Onaolapo, 2024; Aranda & Wardani, 2024; Chindengwike, 2024; Koross et al., 2024; Axad et al., 2022; Khan, 2022). Other measures of financial performance, such as return on assets (ROA) and return on

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equity (ROE), were also (Megeid et al., 2024; Koross et al. 2024; Boniface, 2023). Apart from the fact that most of these studies focused on banks as if it is banks alone that need operational efficiency, most of these studies were conducted outside Nigeria. Unfortunately, due to varying findings, there was no consensus on the actual effect of operational efficiencies on financial performance. Thus, this study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of operational efficiency on the financial performance of industrial goods companies, another sector of the economy.

2.0 REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Operational efficiency

Johnson (2019) defines operational efficiency as a company's ability to manage input and output efficiently. The ability of a company to efficiently manage inputs into outputs is critical to success. Another way of describing operational efficiency is the ability of a company to make use of its resources and prevent waste to deliver high-quality products and services (Ghosh & Sanyal, 2019). Companies can increase profits, competitiveness, and customer satisfaction by implementing the right strategy. According to Olarewaju and Sanusi et al. (2020), operating efficiency measures how well a company can turn financial resources into goods and services at a reduced cost relative to the income it generates. Operational efficiency, defined as a company's capacity to reduce waste and improve asset utilization to provide customers with high-quality goods and services, is influenced by a variety of factors, such as supply chain management, skilled labor, innovative ideas, prudent procurement practices, and economies of scale (Kalluru & Bhat, 2009). Efficient operations can address issues such as unemployment and promote sustainable economic growth; this topic remains significant for both academics and industry experts, particularly in the manufacturing sector.

Operational efficiency can be measured in various ways according to the purpose of using information. According to Kalluru and Bhat (2009), operational efficiency is an organization's capability to abridge unwelcome and boost asset capabilities to convey quality goods and services to clients. Efficiency can be defined as the accuracy of the way of doing something and the ability to perform tasks properly and precisely without wasting excess costs, time, and energy. In the context of economics, Gunawan argues that operational efficiency is the ability to get the job done right or, in mathematical concepts, the ratio between input and output (Mulyadi et al., 2023). Operational efficiency is an important indicator for evaluating bank performance. In the banking context this efficiency includes two main aspects: technical and scale efficiency. According to Bhagavath (2009), the operational efficiency concept has become a concern due to increased competition, business processes, and the evolution of new technology.

2.1.2 Financial performance

Financial performance is a measure of how well a firm can generate returns by using its resources from its most primary business. For a firm to improve overall performance, it should aim at minimizing risk and prepare well for uncertainty. At this time, it is a prerequisite for a firm to know about the determinants of working capital and the appropriate intensity (Mwangi, 2013). Sunusi et al. (2020) defined a company's financial performance as its achievements in a certain period that reflect its health level. In other words, financial performance is an important indicator for assessing a company's effectiveness and efficiency in managing its resources and achieving its goals.

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A company's financial performance can be measured in various ways. The type of measurement used depends on the purpose and the information you want to obtain.

Financial performance is a measure of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms. These results are reflected in the firm's ROI, ROA, shareholder value, accounting profitability, and its components. An entity's financial performance refers to the subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business, generate revenues, and create value for its shareholders (Mboe & Kavale, 2023). Firm performance is affected by multiple external and internal factors. It is important to note that the external factors affecting a firm are across the board and beyond a firm's control. These factors include government rules and regulations, market preference and perception, and the country's economy. According to Baveld (2021), the internal factors that might affect a company's performance are corporate governance practices, ownership structure, risk capital structure, and firm and policies.

2.1.3.1 Inventory turnover and financial performance (FPP)

Inventory turnover indicates how efficiently a company manages its inventory by measuring the number of times inventory is sold and replaced over a period. A higher turnover suggests efficient inventory management, reducing holding costs and obsolescence risk. Inventory turnover compares the cost of goods sold to the cost of inventory. According to Yashim et al. (2020), high turnover can reflect efficient supply chain management and the ability to effectively meet customers' demands, potentially leading to increased sales volume and customer loyalty. Onaolapo (2024) examined the influence of operating efficiency on the financial performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria and found a positive significant effect of inventory turnover on DMBs' financial performances. Koross et al. (2024) determined the effect of operational efficiency on the financial performance of cut-flower farms in Kenya's Nakuru County. The findings showed that efficiency has a significant effect on the financial performance of cut-flower farms in Nakuru County, Kenya. Osazefua (2020) investigated the impact of operational efficiency on the financial sustainability of Nigeria's listed manufacturing companies. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between inventory turnover and return on equity. In contrast, Abdillah (2020) found that inventory turnover has a negative effect on the on assets. Thus, based on the foregoing, this study hypothesized that:

H₀₁: Inventory turnover has no significant effect on the return on capital employed of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria.

2.1.3.2 Receivables' turnover and financial performance

Receivable turnover reflects how quickly a company collects its accounts receivable. A higher turnover implies efficient credit and collection policies, leading to a quicker conversion of sales into cash.. It evaluates the rate at which debtors redeem their debt to the firm and the efficiency of the organization's credit policy and debt collection system (Nyakieni, 2022). A higher receivable turnover indicates that a company efficiently collects its dues from customers on credit sales. According to Megeid et al. (2024), efficient collection reduces the amount of capital tied up in outstanding receivables. This improves the company's working capital position, providing more funds for operational needs or investments, and reducing reliance on external financing costs. Aranda and Wardani (2024) explored the effect of operational efficiency on the financial performance of Islamic banks listed

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on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2019-2023. The results showed that receivable turnover has no significant effect on financial performance, whereas scale efficiency has a significant negative effect. Chindengwike (2024) assessed the connection between operational efficiency and profitability of Tanzanian listed commercial banks on Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE). The findings indicated a statistically significant relationship between commercial banks' profitability and receivable turnover. Boniface (2023) assessed the influence of operating efficiency on Nigeria's industrial firms' financial performance. The results showed that Nigerian industrial enterprises' return on assets is not statistically impacted by accounts receivable turnover. Thus, this study hypothesized that

H₀₂: Receivable turnover has no significant effect on the return on capital employed of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria.

2.1.3.3 Noncurrent Assets Turnover and Financial Performance

Noncurrent assets turnover measures how effectively a company utilizes its noncurrent assets to generate revenue. A higher ratio indicates that the company is generating more sales per naira of assets, signifying efficient asset utilization. Efficient asset utilization often leads to a higher volume of sales generated from the existing asset base. Higher sales directly contribute to increased profitability. A high asset turnover suggests that the company requires fewer assets to generate a given level of sales (Boniface et al., 2023). This implies a more efficient use of capital, as less investment is needed to achieve the same revenue. Megeid et al. (2024) investigated the association between operational efficiency and financial performance of the company on capital structure. Findings revealed that asset turnover and inventory turnover have a significant negative relationship with financial performance. Kurniash and Akhmadi (2024) analyzed the influence of operational efficiency on the company's financial performance mediated by Profitability in companies listed in the JII70 index for 2018-2022. The study's results show that asset turnover does not directly affect the company's financial performance but has an indirect effect through Profitability. Axad et al. (2022) examined the effect of operational efficiency on profitability of listed deposit money banks. The results of the study showed that the total assets turnover, debtors turnover and quick ratio have strong negative impacts on the profitability measured by ROE, of firms. Based, on the foregoing, this study hypothesized that;

H₀₃: Noncurrent assets turnover has no significant effect on the return on capital employed of listed industrial good companies in Nigeria.

2.2 The theoretical framework

The theoretical foundation for this study is the resource dependence theory. Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), proposed by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald Salancik in 1978, offers a valuable framework for understanding how organizations manage their relationships with external entities to secure the necessary resources for survival (Adeniyi & Basse, 2023).

The theory emphasizes that organizations are dependent on external stakeholders for critical resources, such as financial capital, raw materials, and human expertise. Since these resources are crucial to an organization's existence and growth, firms must actively manage and minimize their dependence on external sources, thereby ensuring stability and reducing uncertainties.

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The key premise of RDT is that organizations must strategically manage their relationships with key resources to ensure continuous flow of resources. The moderating effect of RBNs in shaping the firm's strategy and reducing external dependencies cannot be overstated. When firms with industrial goods have access to these critical resources through effective governance practices, their ability to respond to market changes and manage operational risks improves. In turn, these capabilities can reduce investors' perceived risks and increase operational efficiencies (Boniface, 2023). Furthermore, the firm's strategic decisions—such as expanding into new markets or launching new products—can be heavily influenced by the availability of resources and how effectively the board manages relationships with resource providers.

This theory supports this study as it states that efficient internal processes can boost performance. It also supports the fact that efficient resource management is crucial for firms' performance, and this theory provides a framework on how organizations manage dependencies, acquire resources, and improve performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study employed ex-post facto research design this design was suitable for this study because the data used were historical. The study population consisted of 13 industrial good companies, and 11 companies were purposively selected. The data used in this study were obtained from the published annual reports of the sampled industrial good companies and factbooks of the Nigerian Exchange Group during the study period. The method of data analysis employed was pooled regression analysis, and STATA 17 was used for statistical analysis. The model used in this study was adapted from the model specified by Onaolapo (2024), which was modified to fit this study. This model is given as follows:

Financial performance = f (operational efficiency)

$$ROCE_{it} = B_0 + b_1INTO_{it} + b_2RETO_{it} + b_3ASTO_{it} + e_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where;

ROCE = Return on capital employed

INTO = Inventory turnover

RETO = Receivable turnover

ASTO = noncurrent assets turnover

b₀ = Constant

b₁- b₃ = Slope coefficient to be determined in the study

e = Stochastic disturbance

i = ith firm

t = time period

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Table 3.1: Variable operationalization

S/N	Variables	Measurements	Source
Dependent Variable			
1	Return on capital employed (ROCE)	Total revenue/capital employed	Onaolapo (2024)
Independent Variables			
2	Inventory turnover	Sales cost/average inventory	Boniface (2023)
3	Receivable turnover	Sales revenue/average receivable	Odi O (2024)
4.	Noncurrent assets turnover	Sales revenue/current assets	Boniface (2024)

Source: Compilation of the author (2026)

4.0 Analysis and Discussions

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistics of the effect of OE and FP

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
Roce	55	.272	.796	-2.181	4.4
o	55	3.9	5.981	-7.581	42.25
o	55	19.413	23.282	-12.319	91.699
o	55	2.917	3.137	-.154	10.765

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

For the return on capital employed (ROCE), the minimum value was -2.181 while the maximum value was 4.4. On average, industrial good companies in Nigeria recorded a ROCE of 0.272 with a standard deviation of 0.796. This implies that although some firms recorded negative returns, others achieved strong positive returns, with the average showing a modest return relative to the capital employed. The high standard deviation indicates a wide variation in performance across firms, pointing to differences in the efficiency with which companies convert their capital base into profitability.

For inventory turnover (INTO), the lowest was -7.581 and the highest was 42.25. The average was 3.9, with a standard deviation of 5.981. This wide dispersion indicates that while some firms turn over inventory very quickly, others perform poorly, with even negative turnover values in extreme cases. This high variation also implies that significant differences in the efficiency of inventory management among industrial good companies. For RETO the minimum was -12.319 and the maximum was 91.699. On average, the turnover of receivables was 19.413, with a standard deviation of 23.282. This implies that while some firms collected receivables at a fast rate, others were highly inefficient, with some recording negative turnover. The high variation shows a considerable spread in the management practices of receivables across firms in the industrial good sector. For ASTO, the lowest was -0.154 and the highest was 10.765 the average was 2.917 with a standard deviation of 3.137. This indicates that on average, industrial good companies generated close to 3 times their asset base in sales. However, the standard

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deviation reflects moderate to high variation, meaning that some companies used assets more efficiently than others, with a few even recording negative efficiency levels.

Table 4.2 Shapiro–Wilk test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
	55	.645	17.982	.197	.000
into	55	.528	23.936	.810	.000
reto	55	.836	.321	.544	.000
asto	55	.759	12.225	.369	.000

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

From the above output it was revealed that the return on capital employed (ROCE) (p value = 0.000) does not follow a normal curve since the probability/significance level of the z-statistic as revealed by the Shapiro-Wilk test is statistically significant at 5% significance level. The same can be said for the independent variables, inventory turnover (INTO) (p - value 0.000), receivables turnover (RETO) (p - 0.000), and non-current asset turnover (p- value= 0.000), which all appear to follow an abnormal distribution since the probabilities of the z-statistics as revealed by the Shapiro-Wilk test are statistically significant at 5% significance level. Accordingly, CEO educational qualification and CEO origin followed a normal distribution with p values of 0.921 and 1.000, respectively. The probability values were higher than 0.05, assuming normality.

Table 4.3 Spearman’s rank correlation coefficients

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) roce	1.000			
(2) into	-0.120	1.000		
(3) reto	-0.065	0.546	1.000	
(4) asto	0.395	0.077	-0.016	1.000

Spearman rho = -0.016

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

Table 4.3 shows that ROCE had a negligible negative correlation (-0.120) with inventory turnover (INTO). This implies that changes in inventory turnover have no meaningful relationship with the returns generated on capital employed in the firms studied. Similarly, ROCE showed a negligible negative correlation (-0.065) with RETO, implying that RE management has little to no connection with capital efficiency in the sector. Conversely, ROCE had a moderate positive correlation (0.395) with ATO. This indicates that as asset use improves, industrial goods firms’ returns on capital employed tend to although, the relationship is not causative, it implies that efficient use of assets can be associated with improved profitability. For the other firm-level variables, INTO had a strong positive correlation (0.546) with RETO, implies that firms that efficiently manage inventory also tend to be

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effective in collecting receivables. However, INTO showed only a negligible positive correlation (0.077) with ASTO, indicating that inventory efficiency has little association with overall asset use. Finally, RETO and ASTO revealed a negligible negative correlation (-0.016), implying that receivables turnover has practically no relationship with asset turnover in the firms under study. Overall, the presented correlations range from negligible to moderate, confirming the absence of multicollinearity among the variables.

Table 4.4: Regression analysis of the effect of OE on financial performance

	(1) Pooled OLS roce	(2) Panel Random-effects Model roce
into	0.193** (0.040)	0.002 (0.901)
reto	0.310** (0.024)	0.129* (0.050)
asto	0.153** (0.037)	-0.100 (0.897)
Constant	0.477** (0.011)	0.464* (0.078)
r ²	0.383	0.063
N	55.000	55.000
F/W	10.530	4.873
p	0.008	0.082
lagrange		0.50(0.2404)
hottest	3.02(0.0824)	
vif	1.14	

P-values are in parentheses

* P < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The results of the multiple regression analysis are shown in Table 1. The robust model produced an F-statistic of 10.530 with a probability of 0.008, confirming that the model is suitable for statistical inference and that operational efficiency has a statistically significant effect on financial performance. The R-squared value of 0.383 indicates that the proxies of operational efficiency in the model explain approximately 38% of the variation in market capitalization, while the remaining 62% is explained by other factors captured in the error term.

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4.5 Regression assumptions and other diagnostics

Homoscedasticity

The Breusch-Pagan test in Stata 17 was used to examine the OLS model's homoscedasticity assumption. This assumption requires that the error terms have constant variance; otherwise, the regression model's standard errors' reliability may be questioned. The results in Table 4.4 show that this assumption was not violated, as indicated by the heteroscedasticity test outcome ($Hetest = 3.02$, $p\text{-value} = 0.824 < 0.05$). Therefore, we used pooled OLS for statistical inference.

Multicollinearity

The regression model assumes the inexistence of multicollinearity between the predictor variables. It is a situation where one or more independent variables can be expressed as a combination of other variables. This can be detected by observing the VIF. The VIF should be less than 10 for this assumption to hold. From the mean VIF presented in Table 4.4 (1.14), it is safe to say that there were no multicollinearity problems in the dataset.

Lagrange multiplier LM test

The LM test developed by Breusch and Pagan (1980), was used to determine whether the random-effects GLS model or the pooled OLS model was more appropriate for the data. The null hypothesis of the test assumes that there are no random effects, indicating that the variation across entities is negligible and that the pooled OLS model is sufficient. The decision is based on the p-value: if it is greater than 0.05, the null is accepted, and pooled OLS is preferred; otherwise, the null is rejected in favor of a random-effects model. As shown in Tables 4.4 and 4.5, the results revealed a test statistic of 0.50 with a p-value of 0.2404, indicating that the pooled OLS was appropriate for the study.

4.6 Discussion of the findings

Inventory turnover and return on capital employed

The OLS regression analysis results in Table 4.3 show that inventory turnover has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.193; P -value = 0.040) on the return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms during the study period. This implies that a unit increase in the number of times inventory is converted into sales return on capital employed would increase by 20%. The significant positive effect of inventory turnover on ROCE implying that Nigerian industrial goods firms that are more efficient in managing their inventory tend to achieve higher returns on their invested capital. This implies that the ability to rapidly sell off inventory translates into tangible financial benefits. This could be attributed to several factors. First, a faster inventory turnover reduces holding costs, such as warehousing expenses, insurance, and the risk of obsolescence, thereby directly boosting profitability. Second, efficient inventory management can lead to improved cash flow as capital tied up in unsold goods is quickly converted into liquid assets, allowing for reinvestment or debt reduction. Finally, a high turnover might also indicate a strong demand for the firms' products and effective sales strategies. This finding supports the work of Onaolapo (2024), who found that inventory turnover has a positive significant effect on the financial performance of DMBs. However, this finding contradicts the work of Abdillah (2020), who found that inventory turnover has a negative effect on return on assets.

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Receivable turnover and return on capital employed

The OLS regression analysis results in Table 4.3 show that receivable turnover has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.310; P-value = 0.024) on the return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms during the study period. This implies that a unit increase in the number of times receivables are converted into cash would increase the return on capital employed by 30%. The finding that receivable turnover has a significant positive effect on ROCE highlights the importance of efficient credit management and collection practices within the Nigerian IGS. A higher receivable turnover indicates that firms are effectively and quickly collecting payments from their customers. This faster conversion of credit sales into cash improves liquidity, reduces bad debt risk and reduces the need for working capital financing. Consequently, the firm's profitability increases, leading to a higher ROCE. These results implies that Nigerian industrial goods firms should prioritize robust credit policies, efficient invoicing processes, and proactive follow-up mechanisms to ensure timely collection of receivables, thereby positively impacting their financial returns. This finding aligns with Chindengwike's (2024) work, which found statistical significance between commercial banks' profitability and receivable turnover. On the contrary, the finding negates the submission of Boniface (2023), who found that inventory turnover, accounts receivable turnover, or accounts payable turnover does not statistically impact return on assets in Nigerian industrial enterprises.

Noncurrent Assets Turnover and Return on Capital Employed

The OLS regression analysis results in Table 4.3 show that asset turnover has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.153; P -value = 0.037) on the return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms during the study period. This implies that a unit increase in the asset turnover would increase the return on capital employed by 13%. The significant positive effect of asset turnover on ROCE indicates that Nigerian industrial goods firms that effectively utilize their assets to generate sales achieve higher returns on their capital employed. A higher asset turnover implies that the company generates more revenue for each naira invested in its assets. This efficiency in asset use can be attributed to optimal capacity utilization, strategic investments in productive assets, and effective asset management practices. Without a proportional increase in the asset base, increased sales revenue directly contributes to higher profitability and, consequently, a greater ROCE. This finding emphasizes the need for Nigerian industrial goods firms to focus on maximizing their assets' productivity through efficient operations and strategic investment decisions to drive superior financial performance. This finding aligns with the work of Axad et al. (2022), who found that efficiency, as measured by total assets turnover, impacts firms' profitability. However, this finding contradicts the work of Megeid et al. (2024), who found that asset turnover has a significant negative relationship with financial performance.

5.2 Conclusion

This study provided robust empirical evidence that operational efficiency, as measured by inventory turnover, receivable turnover, and asset turnover, exerts a significant positive influence on the financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The findings unequivocally demonstrate that firms consistently achieve superior returns on their capital employed by exhibiting higher rates of inventory turnover, indicating efficient inventory management; higher receivable turnover, reflecting effective credit and collection practices; and higher asset

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turnover, signifying productive asset utilization. These results emphasize the critical role of optimizing internal operational processes as a key driver of financial success within the Nigerian IGS. Thus, operational efficiency has a significant effect on the financial performance of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, the management of industrial goods companies should implement robust strategies to optimize inventory levels, such as improved forecasting techniques, efficient supply chain management, and just-in-time inventory systems where feasible, to minimize holding costs and enhance cash flow. The management of these firms should also develop and enforce robust credit policies, streamline invoicing processes, and establish proactive receivable collection mechanisms to accelerate cash inflows and reduce the risk of bad debt.

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